

**A REVIEW ARTICLE ON THE EFFECT OF VACHADI GANA IN STHAULYA
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ABSTRACT

In modern era, sedentary lifestyle, improper dietary habits and environmental changes have made human being prone to several diseases and Obesity is one among them increasing in prevalence. Overweight and obesity are major risk factors for a number of chronic diseases like Non-Communicable Diseases (NCD) including cardiovascular diseases such as heart disease, Stroke, Diabetes, chronic respiratory diseases, some cancers. In *Ayurved* several drugs of *Ruksha*, *Ushna*, & *Tikshna guna* are mentioned for the management of *Sthoulya*. One of them is *Vachadi Gana* mentioned in different texts of *Ayurved*. *Vachadi Gana* from *Ashtang Hridaya* is taken to study its effect on *Sthoulya*. It consists of six drugs – *Vacha* (*Acorus calamus*), *Nagarmotha* (*Cyperus scariosus*), *Devdaru* (*Cedrus deodara*), *Shunthi* (*Zingiber officinale*), *Atish* (*Aconitum heteropyllum*) and *Haritaki* (*Terminalia chebula*). Purpose of this article is to review the action of drugs of *Vachadi gana* separately in the management of *Sthoulya*. For this several present literature are compiled to know the potential of drugs of *Vachadi gana* in *Sthoulya* management.

KEYWORDS: Obesity, *Sthoulya*, *Vachadi gana*, *Vacha*, *Nagarmotha*, *Devdaru*, *Shunthi*, *Atish*, *Haritaki*.**INTRODUCTION**

Obesity is one among the major diseases of modern era, increasing in prevalence. The World Health report of WHO listed Obesity under top10 selected risks to the health. In 2022, 2.5 billion adults i.e 43% (18 years and older) were overweight. Of these, 890 million i.e 16% were living with obesity.^[1] A body mass index (BMI) over 25 is considered overweight, and over 30 is obese. It is gaining more and more attention of scientists at global level as it is a major risk factor for several other severe diseases. In Modern era, with continuous changing life styles, less physical activity, environment, changed dietary habits, man has become the victim of many diseases and Obesity is one of them. Obesity is the closest entity used for *Sthoulya* and *Atisthula* person is included under *Ashta Nindita purusha* described by Acharya Charak. Hence, *Ashto nindita purusha* are prone to many diseases.^[2]

Sthoulya as described in Ayurvedic texts is caused due to *Mandagni* could be at the level of *Jathragni* or *Dhatwagnijanya* due to *Adhysana*, *Avyayama* and *Divaswapana* & hence formation of “AMA”. *Sthoulya* is considered to be caused due to *Meda Dhatu Dushti*.^[3]

In conventional system of medicine there are drugs, invasive and non invasive procedures which act indirectly on obesity, they reduce the appetite and have adverse effects.

Hence, in order to treat *Sthoulya*, *ama pachan*, *lekhan* and *vata kapha nashan chikitsa* is required. In *Ayurved* classics several drugs are mentioned to achieve the above desired results. One of them is *Vachadi gana* mentioned in the different Ayurvedic Texts – In *Nighantu Adarsh*,^[4] *Sushrut Samhita*^[5], *Ashtang Hridaya*^[6] and *Brihatnighantu Ratnakar*.^[7]

In present study we are discussing about the effect of *Vachadi gana* in *Sthoulya* as mentioned in Ashtang Hridaya. *Vachadi Gana* consists of six ingredients namely – *Vacha*, *Nagarmotha*, *Devdaru*, *Shunthi*, *Atish* and *Haritaki*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the literary review, Classical texts as well as recent research papers and review articles were extensively searched to establish their relevance.

DRUG REVIEW

Table 1: Properties of Drugs of Vachadi Gana.

S.No	Drug Name	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipaak	Dosha pradhanta	Karma
1.	Vacha ^[8]	Tikta, Katu	Tikshna, Laghu	Ushna	Katu	Kapha Vatasham	Krimighna, Deepan, Kanthya Mala mutavishodhani
2.	Nagarmotha ^[9]	Tikta, Katu, Kashaya	Laghu, Ruksha	Sheeta	Katu	Kapha Pittasham	Shothahara, Lekhana, Deepana, Pachana, Kaphaghna, Balya, Mootrala, Grahi
3.	Devdaru ^[10]	Tikta	Laghu, Snigdha	Ushna	Katu	Kapha Vatasham	Deepana, Pachana, Anulomana Kaphanissaraka, Shleshmaputihara, Mootrajanan, Pramehaghna Shothahara,
4.	Shunthi ^[11]	Katu	Laghu, Snigdha	Ushna	Madhur	Kapha Vatasham	Sheetaprashamana, Vedanasthapana, Nadiuttejaka, Shothhara, Rochana, Deepana, Pachana, Vatanulomana, Triptighna, Shool prashmana
5.	Atish ^[12]	Tikta, Katu	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kapha Pittasham	Dipana, Pachana, Samgrahika,
6.	Haritaki ^[13]	Kashay Ras pradhan pancha rasa	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Madhur	Tridosha shamka	Deepan, Rasayana, Chakshushya, Anulomana, Sarvadoshaprashmana, Hrdya, Medhya

Table 2: Chemical Constituents of Vachadi Gana.^[14]

Drug	Chemical Constituents
Vacha	Volatile oil (principal constituent of volatile oil are Asamyl alcohol, eugenol, asarone), Acorin (Glucoside), starch and tannin, acolamone, acoramone, acenone.
Nagarmotha	Pinene, cineol, alcohol – isocyperol, linolenic, linoleic, oleic, myristic and stearic acids and glycerol, oleanolic acid and its glycoside, oleanolic acid- 3-0- neohesperidoside along with sitosterol.
Devdaru	<i>Dihydromyricetin, cedrine, deodorin and cedrin oxide, kaempferol glucoside, polyphenolic lignoids, deodaridone, limonenecarboxylic acid, cedeodarin, dihydromyricetin, cedrin oxide, taxifolin, meso-secoisolaricicresinol, cedrusinin, himacholol, isocentadrol, centadrol, cedrusin, lariciresnol.</i>
Shunthi	Heptane, isovaloraldehyde, camphene, Casinine, myrecene, limonene, phellandrene, curcumene, gingerol, zingerone, shogoal, ginger glycolipids A,B,C gingersols, cineol, gzingeral, gingeodiol, sesquitanjene, zingiberenol, threonine, glycine, isoleucine, leucine and arginine 47
Atish	Atisine, aconitinic acid, tannic acid, oleic, palmitic, stearic glycerides.
Haritaki	Anthraquinone glycoside, Chebulinic acid, chebulin, chebulagic acid, tannic acid, terchebulin, tetrachebulin, vit C, arachidic, behenic, linoleic, oleic, palmitic, stearic acid, maslinic acid.

Vacha

It is a traditional herb used in Indian system of medicine, to treat various health ailments like gastrointestinal,

metabolic (which include obesity, hyperlipidemia etc), respiratory, neurological, kidney, and liver disorders etc and has shown anticonvulsant, antiinflammatory,

immunomodulatory, neuroprotective, cardioprotective, and antiobesity effects.^[15] With its Katu, Tikta Rasa, Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshana Guna, Ushana Virya, Katu Vipaka and Vata Kapha Shamaka property. *Vacha*, a potent component of *Lekhaniya Mahakashaya*, exhibits antiobesity and hypolipidemic properties.^[16]

Nagarmotha

Due to Lekhana, Medoghna, Kapha-Vatahara, Laghu, Ushna and Ruksha Guna, Katu, Tikta, Kashaya Rasa and Katu Vipaka properties of the drug Nagarmotha Choorna. When used with PathyaApathya, accumulated Apachita Meda Dhatu is decreased and thus Motha and Nagarmotha was found beneficial in the study.^[17] The study clearly demonstrated that the bioactive compounds present in *Cyperus rotundus* have promising ability to attenuate the serum lipid profile in high fat diet fed hyperlipidaemic rat model.^[18]

Devadaru

The extracts of *Cedrus deodara* decreased serum glucose, total cholesterol and triglyceride, low density lipoprotein (LDL) and very low density lipoprotein (VLDL) levels and increased high density lipoprotein (HDL) significantly has compared to MSG-control rats.^[19]

It has Katu rasa, Ushna virya, Laghu snigdha guna, Katu vipaka and is Kaphavata samak that helps it in samprapti vighatana. It has Antidiabetic and free radical scavenging activity. Various research studies have substantiated the individual anti-diabetic potential of the herbs including devdaru in Vachadi Gana.^[20]

Shunthi

In Ayurveda, it has been referred as Mahaushadha meaning a great medicine and also Vishvabhesha i.e. the universal medicine. It act as Anulomana, Dipana, Hridya, Pacana, Vatakaphapaha, Asmadoshahara. Many studies have suggested that increasing consumption of plant foods like ginger decreases the risk of obesity, diabetes and heart disease. Ginger is having stimulatory action on heart muscle, and stimulated blood circulation throughout the body. Cardio-tonic effect of gingerol has been observed in guinea pig atrial muscle.^[21] The rhizome cure tumors, ascites, bronchitis, jaundice and mental disorders also have antidiabetic, antidyslipidemic, cardioprotective and antioxidant.^[22] The modern-day research also proves that the drug have hypolipidaemic properties. Thus, helping to restore the normal functions of the body.

Ativisha

It is an Ayurvedic herb which is known for its important medical properties like Deepana, pachana, kaphapittahara. Tikta, katu rasa, laghu, ruksha gunas counteract the guru, snigdha, picchila guna of Kapha & meda, Ushna veerya pacifies kapha.^[23] The root of the plant is used in various forms to prepare various Ayurvedic formulations.

Haritaki

It is called the "King of Medicines" in the Tibet and is always listed first in the Ayurvedic materia medica because of its extraordinary powers of healing with a wide spectrum of biological activity. Haritaki having properties like Kaphaghna, Medoghna, Deepana, Pachana, Ruksha, Laghu Guna, Katu, Tikta Rasa and Ushna Veerya, it does the Sthaulya Samprapti Vighatana. High amount of saponins, phytosterols, chebulinic acid and corilagin present in Haritaki is responsible for the hypolipidemic effect.^[24]

DISCUSSION

This is the era of modernization and fast life as a result people hate to spend energy or invest physical effort in getting their work done and opt for minimal physical activity and fast food. This has led people to fall in the trap of sedentary lifestyle, which has resulted in the emergence of various disorders like metabolic syndrome, which is characterized by the presence of diabetes, obesity, high blood pressure, hyperlipidemia and cardiovascular diseases such as stroke and heart disease are more likely the result of these problems.

Hyperlipidemia is one of the major problems in today's era. Acc to ayurved it is the cause of Santarpanoththa Vyadhis, one among that is Sthoulya. It is given that in Medoroga (obesity) the Srotas are obstructed by Meda and other Dhatus do not get nourished except Meda Dhatu which continues to get accumulated due to lack of Agni. Utility in the treatment of Santarpanoththa Vyadhis is supported by Tikta, Kashaya, Katu Rasa, Laghu - Ruksha Guna, Lekhan Karma and Katu Vipaka of drugs and all these properties are present in drugs of Vachadi Gana. By having Lekhana property these dravyas reduces or scrapes away the unwanted tissues & metabolic wastes. In Sthaulya, there is Sanga type Srotodushti produced by vitiated Kapha and Meda. The drug opens the channels and clears this Sanga (obstruction) in Srotas by the virtue of its Katu Rasa (Marganvivrinoti), Ushna Virya, Pramathi and Srotoshodhan action. Thus, ultimately regulates the functions of Medovaha Srotasa. Due to their deepan and Pachan property they help in proper digestion of food by aggravating Agni. By the above properties of drugs of Vachadi Gana it is found to be effective in the management of Sthoulya.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of different studies concluded from various Ayurvedic texts and research articles it can be concluded that drugs of Vachadi gana that includes Vacha, Devdaru, Nagarmotha, Shunthi, Atish, Haritaki having Tikta, Katu, Kashaya Rasa, Katu Vipaka, Ushna veerya, and Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshana guna reduces Agnimandya and restore the Agni at dhatu level which in turn checks the process of Dhatuvrudhhi (improperly nourish dhatu) and decreases Dhatushaithilya which in turn helps alleviate Obesity.

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